

REVOICES (Reetta Toivanen)

This dataset consists of handwritten notes and interviews with persons who experienced forced movement or expulsion from today's Poland and Czech Republic to today's Germany, or their descendants. The notes consists of observations and discussions with several persons. The discussions have been carried out in order to test the feasibility of a research proposal and will be used as any other ethnographic material.

- Dates: 2021-2025
- Keywords: Expulsion, Second World War, Europe, Peace building, Refugeeeness, Silencing
- Author: Prof. Dr. Reetta Toivanen, Centre of Excellence in Law, Identity and European Narratives, University of Helsinki
- Publications in process:
Toivanen, R. Forthcoming Silence to Statute: How Europe's Postwar Refugee Past Shapes Law and Belonging, *Journal of Unofficial Law and Legal Pluralism*, writing.
Toivanen, R. Refugee Memory, Racialisation, and the Colonial-Modern Imaginary in Postwar Europe, *Social Anthropology*, writing.
- The data is stored in onedrive behind password and at home in different booklets without any information about the informants.